

Synthesis of New Anilido-Pyrazoline and Isoxazoline Derivatives

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Interaction of acetoacetanilide(Ia) or its hydroxy derivative(Ib) with aromatic (or heterocyclic) aldehydes gave the corresponding α, β -unsaturated ketones(II). The reaction of alcoholic solution of (II) with hydrazine hydrate or hydroxylamine in a basic catalyst gave the corresponding pyrazoline or isoxazoline derivatives.

EXTENSIVE efforts have been made to prepare new members of pyrazolines¹⁻¹¹ and isoxazolines^{8-10, 12-14}. But, those containing anilido group were not mentioned before. In this work new anilidopyrazolines and isoxazolines were prepared.

Experimental

The ir spectra were determined with a unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer using the KBr wafer technique. All melting points are uncorrected.

Synthesis of aceto-*o*-hydroxyacetanilide(Ib) :

To a preheated ethylacetoacetate (40 ml, 0.015 mole) at 110°, *o*-aminophenol (25 gm, 0.01 mole) was added. The reaction mixture was warmed at 100-110° for 30-40 min. Then allowed to cool, where colourless needles from (Ib) were separated. The product was filtered off, washed, with few ml ether and crystallised from ethanol into colourless needles, m.p. 110°, Anal. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₁O₃N : C, 62.18 ; H, 5.70 ; N, 7.25. Found : C, 62.30 ; H, 5.80, N, 7.12.

Synthesis of anilido- α, β -unsaturated ketone derivatives(II) :

A mixture of equimolecular amounts (0.05 mole) from Ia¹⁵ or Ib and the aldehyde was fused for 10-15 min, the reaction mixture was cooled and digested with petroleum ether (60-80), the separated product (II) was filtered off, washed with petroleum ether and crystallised from methanol-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 4). Yield 60-70%. The anilido- α, β -unsaturated ketones(II) are coloured compounds ranging from yellow to orange-red, readily soluble in alcohols, acetic acid, dioxan, chloroform and carbontetrachloride ; sparingly soluble in petroleum ether. The results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—3-ANILIDO (OR *o*-HYDROXYANILIDO)-4-ARYL (OR FURYL)-BUT-3-ENE-2-ONE(II)

X, R	m.p. °C	X, R	m.p. °C
(a) H, C ₆ H ₅ -	110	(g) OH, C ₆ H ₅ -	100
(b) H, <i>o</i> -OH - C ₆ H ₄ -	85	(h) OH, <i>o</i> -OH - C ₆ H ₄ -	190
(c) H, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	75	(i) OH, <i>o</i> -, <i>p</i> -(OH) ₂ - C ₆ H ₃ -	185
(d) H, <i>p</i> -Cl - C ₆ H ₄ -	170	(j) OH, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	120
(e) H, C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	120	(k) OH, <i>p</i> -Cl - C ₆ H ₄ -	92
(f) H, C ₄ H ₉ O -	90	(l) OH, C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH -	125

All compounds gave satisfactory analysis.

Synthesis of *N*-acyl-3-methyl-4-anilido-5-methylpyrazolines(III) :

A mixture of anilido- α, β -unsaturated ketones (II, 0.01 mole), hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mole), ethanol (20 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 6-8 hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled and poured on to ice-water, when the pale coloured products(III) were separated. They were filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1). Yield 70-75%. The results are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2—N-ACETYL-3-METHYL-4-ANILIDO-5-ARYLPYRAZOLINES(III)

X, R	m.p. °C	X, R	m.p. °C
(a) H, C ₆ H ₅ -	130	(g) OH, <i>o</i> -OH - C ₆ H ₄ -	210
(b) H, <i>o</i> -OH - C ₆ H ₄ -	135	(h) OH, <i>o</i> -, <i>p</i> -(OH) ₂ - C ₆ H ₃ -	>350 (d. 280)
(c) H, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	140	(i) OH, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	155
(d) H, C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	170	(j) OH, <i>p</i> -Cl - C ₆ H ₄ -	120
(e) H, C ₄ H ₉ O	160	(k) OH, C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	185
(f) OH, C ₆ H ₅ -	133		

All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Synthesis of N-phenyl-3-methyl-4-anilido-5-arylpyrazolines(IV) :

A mixture of equimolecular amounts of II and phenylhydrazine (0.005 mole), ethanol (30 ml) and piperidine (0.5 ml) was refluxed for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled and poured on to acidified ice-water (HCl). The separated products (IV) filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from methanol-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 3). Yield 75-80%. These pyrazolines are soluble in alcohols, chloroform, dioxane, benzene ; sparingly soluble in petroleum ether. The results are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—N-PHENYL-3-METHYL-4-ANILIDO-5-ARYLPYRAZOLINE(IV)

X, R	m.p. °C	X, R	m.p. °C
(a) H, C ₆ H ₅ -	120	(g) OH, o-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	140
(b) H, o-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	125	(h) OH, o-, p-(OH) ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ -	>300 (d 270)
(c) H, p-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	130	(i) OH, p OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	128
(d) H, C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	100	(j) OH, p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	120
(e) H, C ₆ H ₅ O -	110	(k) OH, C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	150
(f) OH, C ₆ H ₄ -	135		

All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Synthesis of 3-methyl-4-anilido-5-arylisoxazolines(V) :

A mixture of (II, 0.005 mole), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.0075 mole), ethanol (30 ml) and potassium hydroxide (0.0075 mole) was refluxed for 10 hr. The separated products obtained after cooling and pouring on to cold water were filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from methanol-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 3). Yield 70-75%. The pale coloured isoxazoline derivatives(V) are readily soluble in alcohols, dioxane, chloroform ; sparingly soluble in benzene and insoluble in petroleum ether. The results are listed in Table 4.

TABLE 4—3-METHYL-4-ANILIDO-5-ARYLISOXAZOLINES(V)

X, R	m.p. °C	X, R	m.p. °C
(a) H, C ₆ H ₅ -	120	(f) OH, C ₆ H ₅ -	135
(b) H, o-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	350	(g) OH, o-, p-(OH) ₂ - C ₆ H ₄ -	350 (d 200)
(c) H, p-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	165	(h) OH, p-OCH ₃ - C ₆ H ₄ -	145
(d) H, C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	130	(i) OH, p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	130
(e) H, C ₆ H ₅ O -	>350	(j) OH, C ₆ H ₅ - CH=CH -	155

Biological screening for selected pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives (III, IV and V) :

The culture medium was normal nutrient agar (N.A.) medium¹⁶ supplemented with one gram yeast/litre, the bacterial suspension was prepared by adding one ml of sterile distilled water to a 24 hr old culture of the test organism grown on N.A. slant. One ml aliquots of bacterial suspension were added to Erlenmeyer flasks containing 150 ml of N.A. and the flasks were incubated for 24 hr.

Petri dishes containing sterile modified N.A. were flooded with the bacterial suspension of the test organisms (2 plates for each organism). Two filter paper discs (one cm diameter) containing the selected compounds (III, IV and V), dissolved in ethyleneglycol (10 mg/L.), were placed on each plate. The plates were incubated at 37° for 24 hr and the diameter of the inhibition zone was measured. The experiments were repeated 3 times and the results obtained were averaged. The results are given in Table 5.

TABLE 5—BACTERIOLOGICAL SCREENING OF SELECTED ANILIDOPYRAZOLINE AND ISOXAZOLINE COMPOUNDS

Organism used	III	IV	V
<i>Staphylococcus albus</i>	+	-	-
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	+	Slight	+
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	Slight	-	-
<i>Sarcina lutea</i>	+	+	+

Results and Discussion

The condensation of aldehydes and acetoacetanilide (Ia) and or aceto-o-hydroxyacetanilide (Ib) gave the corresponding anilido- α , β -unsaturated ketones(II). Their' ir spectra showed strong absorption bands at 1690 cm⁻¹ (conjugated carbonyl groups), 1600 cm⁻¹ (olefinic double bond) and 3320 cm⁻¹ (NH).

Synthesis of anilidopyrazolines(III) and (IV) :

3-Anilido-4-arylbut-3-ene-3-one(II) derivatives, when treated with hydrazine hydrate and or phenylhydrazine, gave the corresponding anilidopyrazoline derivatives(III) and (IV). These compounds showed

absorption bands at 1230 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{ C-N}$), 1600 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{ C=N}$), 3320 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{ NH}$) and 1660 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{ C=O}$) and also gave Knorr's colour test¹⁷ characteristic for arylpyrazolines.

Synthesis of anilidoisoxazolines(V) :

Interaction of (II) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of KOH gave the corresponding anilidoisoxazolines. The ir spectra of these compounds showed absorption bands at 1600 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{ C=N}$) 3320 cm^{-1} , 1660 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{ NH}$, C=O).

Bactericidal activity of selected compounds were tested against some gram positive and gram negative bacteria and it was found that these compounds have a remarkable activity, specially against *Sarcina lutea* and *Bacillus subtilus*.

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